
DIGITAL RESEARCH SKILLS AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF ACADEMICS IN FEDERAL UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH- SOUTH, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their digital research skills in Federal Universities in south-south Nigeria. To achieve the aim of the study, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Ex-post facto research design was used for the study. The study population consisted of all the 7,107 male and female academics in all the seven federal universities from the six South-South states. 1,393 participants representing 20% of the academic staff population were drawn from the four sampled universities in south-south zone of Nigeria using Multi-stage sampling approach (comprising stratification, purposive and simple random sampling). Digital Research Skills Questionnaire (DRSQ) and 'Job Performance of Academics questionnaire (JPAQ) were used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using internal consistency method. The DRSQ and JPAQ were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Analysis and the reliability indices of 0.86 and 0.80 were obtained respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that, male and female academics in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their operational online search skills, but did not differ significantly in their job performance based on their generic online search skills. It is recommended amongst others that, more opportunities should be provided to both male and female academics in form of training, retraining, seminars and workshop so that academics acquire online search skills such as operational online search skills so that they can be more effective in their job performance.

Key words: *Digital research skills, in Federal Universities in south-south, academics, operational online search skills, generic online search skills.*

Introduction

The goal of information and communication technology in education as enshrined in the National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in Education by Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2019) is to meet the human capital requirements of the nation for attaining and enhancing sustainable socio-economic development, global competitiveness as well as the individual's ability to survive in a contemporary environment using ICT. The objectives of ICT in Education are to: facilitate the teaching and learning processes, promote problem-solving, critical thinking and innovative skills, and foster research and development among others.

In the university, academics are known for teaching, research and community service. Academics, male or female make use of ICT for their service delivery (otherwise known as job performance) especially in teaching and research. Performance is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals. Job performance is the degree to which an academic or scholar can effectively combine duties (such as teaching, research and community service) (Mbon *et al.*, 2019; Odigwe *et al.*, 2020; Owan *et al.*, 2020). It is the measure of the effectiveness of academics in relation to their roles and responsibilities in their work place. Taiwo (2014) opined that Job performance is the overall expected value from employees' behaviours carried out over the course of a set period of time. Okoi and Odigwe, (2018) explained that academic staff job performance is the association between teaching features and educational success in the classroom. It could therefore be deduced that academics' performances in the universities are basically measured by their research output, quality of teaching and community services. However, job performance is delimited to teaching and research in this study. Academics are expected to administer continuous assessment in form of class test, take home assignments, and supervise students in their research works. They are also expected to write journal articles and attend national and international conferences, seminars and workshops. Digital search skills are always on hand to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out these activities. This could help them meet their job demands and engender positive work life. Digital search skills allow quicker access to study materials through the internet. The use of online search to access journals, periodicals, magazines, inaugural lectures, conference papers could help a lecturer to grow fast on the job and in the long run; the stress that comes with teaching and research work is reduced minimally. In their service delivery, it appears that many perform their jobs effectively while some do not. Some find it difficult to update knowledge in their respective areas of specialisation. This could possibly be influenced by one's knowledge of the ICT, especially the digital research skills.

Digital research skills are the user's ability to pose a query to an information system in order to fulfil a specific request. Online Search skills are required not only for gaining access to the available information resources, but also to sift from the large quantity and optimise the most appropriate information. Online search skills are essential for effectively navigating, finding, evaluating and utilizing information on the internet. Liu and Sun (2012) defined online search skills as the cognitive and technical abilities required to use search tools to locate, assess and synthesize information from digital sources. Hock (2013) opined that online search skills encompass the methods and strategies employed to retrieve information effectively while critically evaluating the credibility and relevance of sources. In other words, online search skills are the ability to locate content online effectively and efficiently. Van Deursen (2014) posited that digital research skills include among others the operational and generic online search skills.

An operational online search skill is the foundational competency required to operate computers, get started with internet connections in order to perform online searches efficiently, as such it covers basic entry interactions with online search. It also includes the ability to book mark website, use the different types of field (buttons), save the information or materials into storage, open and manage browser windows or tabs. Operational skills, therefore, sets an individual on the path of being able to perform other online search skill like formal online skills. Formal online search skill refers to the structured technical abilities that are required to use search engines, digital tools and online resources systematically and effectively, but particularly, it focuses on formal methods and advanced features on online searches. It includes the ability to apply file type and domain to narrow results, use navigation techniques within specific platforms and specialized search tools such as Google scholar, data base searches or PubMed for specific information. Formal online search skills can be complimented with information online search skills. Information online search skills are skills needed to effectively search for, access, and extract relevant information from online sources, while focusing on identifying credible information and synthesizing results. With information skill, academics have the ability to locate, evaluate and use the needed information effectively. Goulding and Spacey (2012) found that men possess more knowledge about the internet and the way to use it than women since the latter have been slower to start using the internet than men have. Also, a study by Hew and Leong (2011) revealed that males were more skillful in dimension of operational skill and use more computers than the females do. Bassi and Camble (2011) also reported that there exists a statistical difference between males and females in using electronic resources as females have more difficulty in finding information online than males. Another needed skill is the generic online search skills.

Generic online search skill is defined as critical thinking, analytical reasoning, problem-solving and written communication skill. Generic skill refers to such cognitive abilities as learning-to-learn, analysis and problem solving, innovation (Tuononem *et al* 2022). Such generic online search skill enables new applications to be learned as they become functionally relevant. With generic online skill, academics can know if the device they are using is connected to other sites, what information is passing over that connection, if the information is protected from eavesdroppers, alteration and the authenticity of such information. Tsai (2009) examined high school students' online search strategies and found that male students had better behavioural and procedural strategies than females, but no significant difference was found between their metacognitive strategies. Nian and Rashid (2022) also found that there is a high level of relationship between generic skills and level of job performance among STEM teachers in Malaysia. Feng *et al.* (2011) found a gender differences in visual reflexive attention shifting.

The interplay of all these digital search skills could play an important role in the job performance of academics in the universities. It is arguable that some individuals experience difficulties in customizing search terms, reasoning with the search results, having a critical attitude towards the resource, and organizing the search process. The online search skill difficulty is sometimes debated to be more prevalent with males than females. In the words of King and Blandford (2002), females view technology as less of a threat when they perceive computers as a method of communication and not as computational, while others argues for males than females. Chen and Tsai (2007) also reported that males exhibited more favourable attitudes toward web-based learning than females. Their results suggested that males perceived the proliferation and development of the internet to result in a better tool which reduces the digital divide and establish a society of equity and justice.

From the foregoing, it appears that the evidence for specific gender differences in online search skill and its effect on job performance is inconclusive although there is a widespread belief that computers and the internet are male dominated technologies. Therefore, the need to examine the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their digital research skills in Federal Universities in south-south Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Academics landscape is continuously evolving, today it is driven by technological advancements and changing educational demands; with these, it appears that some academics struggle to navigate the complexities of modern research environments which require not only expertise in their subject matter but also proficiency in digital tools. It appears that some academics do not prepare adequately for classroom activities; some do not regularly attend seminars, conferences and workshops to enhance their research work. Moreover, some seem not to be interested in carrying out research, as they find it difficult to employ digital tools in searching for relevant information for lectures, conference, and workshop, among others.

These anomalies could be associated with lack of digital research skills by some academics. It is through these skills that academics access, evaluate and utilize information effectively to improve job performance. In a bid to solving this problem, the gender disparities that exists in the development and application of this skills, has caught many scholars' attention. Some scholars argue that more male acquire more digital research skills than the female counterparts while others argue in favour of the female academics. These differences may influence their ability to locate relevant literature, conduct thorough research and ultimately contribute to their productivity and career advancement. Despite the importance of online search skills in supporting academic work, the difference in job performance of male and female academics due to online search skills is yet to be ascertained. Therefore, what is the difference in male and female academics' job performance based on their digital research skills in federal universities in south-south Nigeria?

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised:

- i. What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their operational online search skills in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their generic online search skills in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested on 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skills in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their generic online search skills in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria.

Methods

This study adopted Ex-post facto research design. It was conducted in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The South-South Nigeria is one out of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and it comprises of six states which are: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers states. The population comprised 7,107 male and female academics in

all the seven federal universities from the six South-South states. These comprise of University of Uyo, Uyo (1202), The Federal University of Petroleum Resources Effurun located in Delta state (189), Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa (428), Nigerian Maritime University Okerenkoko Delta State (100), The University of Port-Harcourt (1238), University of Benin (1896), and University of Calabar (2054). The sample size of the study was 1,393 participants representing 20% of the academic staff population drawn from the four sampled universities in south- south zone of Nigeria using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Sample Size Determination Table. Multi-stage sampling approach (comprising stratification, purposive and simple random sampling) was used to select the sample of the study.

Digital Research Skills Questionnaire (DRSQ) and ‘Job Performance of Academics questionnaire (JPAQ)’ were used for data collection. The DRSQ was divided into two sections: A and B. Section A was used to elicit response on demographic variables such as gender, while section B contained 14 developed items used to collect data on the operational online search skills and generic online search skills. Similarly, the JPAQ comprised of 20 items, developed on job performance of academic’s on research and teaching. Both instruments were measured on a four points rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD). To establish the internal consistency of the instruments, an inter-item approach was used. The scores obtained from 50 academics that were not part of the sample used for the study were collated and subjected to Cronbach’s Alpha statistical tool. The result of the analysis was established as 0.86 for DRSQ and 0.80 for JPAQ. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for testing hypotheses was to reject the null hypotheses, if the calculated F is greater than the critical F or retain the null hypothesis if the calculated F is less than the critical F-value. In answering the research questions, the decision rule applied was 1-2.5 (Not Acquired), 2.5-4.00 (Acquired). Therefore, academics with the higher mean were considered to perform better in their job than academics with the lower mean.

Results

Research Question One

What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skill in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skill

Gender	Operational Online Search skill	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	Acquired	52.06	17.72	685
	Not Acquired	46.15	16.75	310
	Total	50.22	17.63	995
Female	Acquired	34.51	6.66	229
	Not Acquired	35.34	7.85	146
	Total	34.83	7.15	375
Total	Acquired	47.66	17.44	914
	Not Acquired	42.69	15.35	456

The entries in Table 1 showed the descriptive statistics on job performance of male and female academics based on their operational online search skill. Results as presented in the Table reveals the mean and standard deviations for the difference in job performance of male

and female academics based on operational online search skill. It shows the job performance means of male who acquired operational online search skills as: 52.06 and those who do not acquire with 46.15, also female who acquire operation online search skills with job performance mean score of 34.51 and those who do not acquire with 35.34 respectively. This shows that male academics who acquired operational online search skills performed better in their job than female academic staff in federal universities in south-South, Nigeria. Therefore male and female academics differ in their job performance based on their operational online search skill.

Research Question two

What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performance of male and female academics, based on generic online search skill.

Gender	Generic Online Search skill	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	Acquired	51.82	17.66	619
	Not Acquired	47.55	17.28	376
	Total	50.22	17.63	995
Female	Acquired	35.06	7.10	240
	Not Acquired	34.44	7.26	135
	Total	34.84	7.15	375
Total	Acquired	47.16	17.19	859
	Not Acquired	44.08	16.34	511
	Total	46.01	16.94	1370

The entries in Table 2 showed the descriptive statistics on job performance of male and female academics based on their generic online search skill. Results as presented in the Table 4.7 reveals the result of Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill. It shows the job performance means of male who acquired generic online search skill as: 51.82 and those who do not acquire with 47.55, also female who acquire generic online search skills with job performance mean score of 35.06 and those who do not acquire with 34.44 respectively. This shows that male academics who acquired generic online search skills performed better in their job than female academic staff in federal universities in south-South, Nigeria. Also, the result also shows that the standard deviations of the scores for the male and female academics are above 1 (17.66, 17.28, 7.10, and 7.26). Therefore male and female academics differ in their job performances based on their generic online search skill.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skills in Federal Universities in south-south, Nigeria

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of the difference in operational online search skill of male and female academics based on job performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	71987.664	3	23995.888	102.204	.000
Intercept	1776570.848	1	1776570.848	7566.803	.000
Gender	50574.428	1	50574.428	215.408	.000
Operational Online	1617.114	1	1617.114	6.888	.009
Gender * Operational Online	2863.370	1	2863.370		.000
Error	320716.149	1366	234.785		
Total	3293096.000	1370			
Corrected Total	392703.813	1369			

*significant at .05 alpha level

The result in Table 3 reveals the result of ANOVA for the significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skill. The result shows the F value of 12.196 with its corresponding significant value of .000 with 1 and 1366 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore, the null hypothesis which claimed a no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skills is rejected. The result implies that there is a significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skills in federal universities in South-South, Nigeria

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill in Federal Universities in south-south, Nigeria

Table 4: Analysis of Variance of the difference in generic online search skill of male and female academics based on job performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	68831.672	3	22943.891	96.771	.000
Intercept	1799824.846	1	1799824.846	7591.146	.000
Gender	56394.125	1	56394.125	237.854	.000
generic Online	1530.860	1	1530.860	6.457	.011
Gender * generic Online	852.046	1	852.046		.058
Error	323872.141	1366	237.095		
Total	3293096.000	1370			
Corrected Total	392703.813	1369			

* Not significant at .05 alpha level

The result in Table 4 reveals the result of ANOVA for the significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill. The result shows the F value of 3.594 with its corresponding significant value of .058 with 1 and 1366 degrees of freedom. The result is not significant; hence, the null hypothesis which claimed a no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill is retained. This means that there is no significant difference in job

performance of male and female academics based on generic online search skill in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

Operational Online Search Skills and Job Performance of Academics

Findings of the study from research question one revealed that male and female academics in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their operational online search skill. This means that male academics possess operational online search skills more than their female counterparts that influence their job performance. Also data analysis for hypothesis one indicates that there is a significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skill in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria. Consequently, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on operational online search skill is rejected. The turnout of this result could be attributed to the fact that male academics are more confident in using mouse and the keyboard, copying and retrieving information from a storage device such as flash drive and disk, bookmark websites as well as being able to convert information from one format to another (e.g. word to pdf) among others which could enhance job performance more than their female counterpart. The male academics are also able to use more common programmes such as Microsoft Word or Excel or specialized programmes, such as the bookkeeping programme, QuickBooks, to promote their job performance and work on more challenging projects or tasks in the department. The gender divide could be explained by socio-cultural preconceptions about interactions of women with technologies and attitude towards domestic responsibilities.

The findings of this study is also in tandem with that of Goulding and Spacey (2012) whose result revealed that men possess more knowledge about the internet and the way to use it than women since the latter have been slower to start using the internet than men have. This is supported by the findings of Hew and Leong (2011) whose findings revealed that males were more skilful in dimension of operational skill and use more computers than the females do. The findings of this study is also in agreement with the findings of Bassi and Camble (2011) who reported that there exists a statistical difference between males and females in using electronic resources as females have more difficulty in finding information online than males.

Generic Online Search Skill and Job Performance of Academics

Findings of the study from research question seven revealed that male academics possess Generic online search skills more than their male counterparts and as such influences their job performance. Also data analysis for hypothesis two revealed that there is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on Generic Online search skills in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

However, the absence of significant differences in job performance of male and female academics based on Generic Online search skills in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria might be attributed to differences in methodology, or might reveal how the increasing number of female Internet users is altering women's attitudes regarding computers and the Web. It could also be attributed to the fact that women sometimes have higher cognitive test scores than men and as such, the differences in job performance of male and female academics cannot be explained by the difference in generic online search skills. This findings is in line with Tsai (2009) who examined high school students' online search strategies and reported that male students had better behavioural and

procedural strategies than females, but no significant difference was found between their metacognitive strategies.

The finding is not in agreement with that of Nian and Rashid (2022) whose findings showed that there is a high level of relationship between generic skills and level of job performance among STEM teachers in Malaysia. The finding is at variance with the findings Feng *et al.* (2011), which revealed gender differences in visual reflexive attention shifting. They indicated that Gender differences in visual attention shifting may moderate or contribute to gender differences in other cognitive activities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that male and female academics in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their operational online search skills, but do not differ significantly in their job performance based on their generic online search skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. More opportunities should be provided to both male and female academics in form of training, retraining, seminars and workshop so that academics acquire online search skills such as operational online search skills so that they can be more effective in their job performance.
- ii. University management should strengthen access to research scholarships, funding's, grants and incentives especially to female academics. Certain waivers can be granted to them due to their domestic responsibilities to enhance job performance through formal online search skills.

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